

Temporal and Doppler Coherence Limits for the Underwater Acoustic Channel during the LCAS'15 High Duty Cycle Sonar Experiment

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Abstract— Unlike conventional Pulsed Active Sonar (PAS) which listens for target echoes in between short-burst transmissions, High Duty Cycle (HDC) sonar attempts to detect echoes amidst the continual interference from source(s) transmitting with nearly 100% duty cycle. Continuous transmission waveforms may be of several types. Linear Frequency Modulated waveforms (LFMs) provide good range measurements but less accurate target Doppler; Continuous Wave signals (CWs) provide good Doppler measurements but less accurate target range. More sophisticated waveforms (e.g. PRNs) attempt to combine the positive effects of both of these waveforms. The potential advantage of HDC waveforms is either increased time-bandwidth product processing gain, or an increased number of detection opportunities, depending on the selection of the sonar receiver's processing time window (interval). For continuous time LFM (CTLFM) waveforms, very large time-bandwidth products can be achieved (about more than one order of magnitude larger than PAS waveforms). However, there are practical limits to the amount of coherent time-bandwidth gain that is achievable, due to the temporal and Doppler spreading effects of the underwater acoustic channel. This paper investigates the temporal and Doppler coherence limits of the underwater channel experienced during the Littoral Continuous Active Sonar 2015 experiment (LCAS'15), and compares them to theoretical expectations.

Keywords— *continuous active sonar; high duty cycle sonar; continuous time LFM, channel coherence, Doppler, multipath*

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been emerging interest in the concept of High Duty Cycle (HDC) Sonar. Unlike Pulsed Active Sonar (PAS), which listens for echoes in between short transmission bursts, HDC sonar attempts to detect echoes amidst the continual interference from source(s) transmitting with nearly 100% duty cycle. A schematic of the two contrasting approaches is shown in Fig. 1. A potential advantage of HDC sonar is an increased number of continuous detection opportunities, leading to improved target detection, localization, tracking, and classification. In addition, lower transmission source levels are possible. Of course, appropriate HDC-specific processing must be employed to enable detection in the presence of continuous transmissions.

Like PAS systems, HDC sonar systems may employ a variety of signal types. Single FM waveforms provide good

target ranging measurements, but no Doppler information. Conversely, CW waveforms provide good target Doppler (range-rate) measurements, but poor ranging information. Sonar systems, including multistatic systems, can gain valuable geometrically complementary detection opportunities when both signal types are used [1]. Finally, one may consider sophisticated broadband waveforms which attempt to provide both good range and Doppler measurements simultaneously.

Fig. 1. Depiction of three cycles of PAS (top, blue) and HDC (bottom, red) transmission methods. The PAS “listens after transmitting” and the HDC method “listens while transmitting”. T_{pri} is the ping repetition interval and T is the LFM signal duration.

High Duty Cycle waveforms are continuously repeated with a certain cycle time, corresponding to a PAS system's ping repetition interval (T_{pri}). T_{pri} defines the maximum range at which targets may be detected without becoming ambiguously associated with previous waveform cycles. For HDC waveforms, very long duration signals are possible, up to the duration of the T_{pri} , which enables very large time-bandwidth (TB) products: an order of magnitude or more than is available with a PAS waveform. Theory suggests that increasing the TB product in processing will improve resolution in the time and/or Doppler dimensions and thereby increase the SNR in reverberation and/or noise-limited conditions, respectively. This is done by reducing the acoustic background, either by

increasing the signal duration (to reduce ambient noise) or by increasing the signal bandwidth (to reduce reverberation), or both, while leaving the signal level un-diminished. However, to achieve such theoretical gains without signal losses for high TB signals, the following conditions are required:

- There is no multipath propagation from source-to-target-to-receiver in the environment, such as from acoustic refraction effects and reflections from boundaries
- There is no Doppler spreading induced by propagation in the environment, such as the modulation imparted by reflections from a dynamic, rough sea surface, or other effects.
- The target is a “point target”, or effectively a point target with physical dimensions smaller than the sonar’s observation cell size.
- There is no Doppler shift (i.e., range-rate) based on the kinematics between the source, target, and receiver.
- If there is Doppler shift (range-rate), it must be constant Doppler without accelerations and, appropriate Doppler-matched processing is performed to avoid the smearing effect of processing large TB waveforms (this is necessary even for FM waveform which typically does not require it) [2].

Since these assumptions will not be completely valid for an operational sonar in a real environment, there will be some practical limitations to achieving large TB processing gains based on the resulting signal losses. Processing signals of longer duration than the Doppler coherence limit that the channel supports, or wider bandwidth than the temporal coherence limit that the channel supports, may not be the most effective use of HDC waveforms. Alternatively, processing subsets of the transmitted HDC pulse cycle may be a more effective methodology. HDC sonar presents an additional processing parameter, not available with PAS, which may be used to tune the performance of the sonar to local environmental conditions and to the scenario of interest. This parameter is the processing interval (T_p): how much time (out of the continuous active sonar’s cycle time) is used for coherent processing. In the case of the Continuous Time Linear Frequency Modulated (CTLFM) signal, T_p corresponds to a processed sub-bandwidth (B_p), as depicted in Fig 2. The sonar operator can choose T_p within the bounds of: $0 < T_p \leq T_{pri}$. The choice will be a tradeoff between how much time-bandwidth to use for SNR gain vs. the number of detection opportunities available within a single T_{pri} . The possibility of achieving more detection opportunities, with a much higher update rate, may provide improvements in cumulative probability of detection, target initiation and holding, and target localization [3].

This paper investigates the coherence limits of an underwater acoustic channel in both time and Doppler, which

can then inform the judicious selection of T_p for HDC processing. The general effects of time and bandwidth are discussed in Section II. Section III describes the LCAS’15 sea trial. Section IV shows single ping ambiguity function results from the sea trial and Section V gives the results of a statistical analysis using all of the data in a run. Section VII provides a summary and conclusions.

Fig. 2. Depiction of an example LFM signal in time and frequency vs. time. Yellow indicates the processing subband and green indicates the processing interval.

II. PERFORMANCE VS. PROCESSING TIME/BANDWIDTH

The LFM range resolution is approximately given by

$$\Delta r \approx \frac{c}{2B_p} \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of sound in water. The LFM Doppler resolution is approximated by

$$\Delta v \approx \frac{1}{T_p} \quad (2)$$

Processing smaller TB segments at faster update rates will decrease measurement resolution in both time and Doppler. The impact of this is twofold: first, the echo’s signal-to-background ratio (SBR) may be reduced; second, the decrease in resolution means more uncertainty in the target’s range position and Doppler. Processing larger TB at slow rates will increase measurement resolution and SBR will improve, but will match theoretical predictions only until the point where signal coherence in the channel breaks down.

Some sectors of the surveillance space may be limited by reverberation; others may be limited by noise. Reductions in T_p and B_p will lead to larger observation cells in range and Doppler, respectively. Within these larger cells, more noise or reverberation will enter and raise the acoustic background level measured in the cell. This results in a loss in the SBR and decreased detectability. The theoretical SBR processing gains against background noise and reverberation cases are approximated as

$$PG_{noise} \sim 10 * \log_{10}(T_p), \quad (3)$$

$$PG_{reverb} \sim 10 * \log_{10}(B_p). \quad (4)$$

Therefore, doubling the processing time should provide about a 3 dB gain against noise, while doubling bandwidth should provide a similar 3 dB gain against reverberation. However, this assumes that only the acoustic (reverberation or noise) background will be reduced, and that the received signal level will not experience any losses. The signal losses referred to here are processing losses due to changes in signal bandwidth or duration; we are not discussing here the normal propagation (transmission) losses any received signal is subject to. In real underwater acoustic environments, such signal losses will occur when the waveform resolution in time or frequency, or both, is finer than the environmental spreading of the signal energy. In the time dimension, this is sometimes referred to as energy splitting loss (ESL), and such losses can be predicted using the Bell Jones model [4]. In some sonar processing schemes the ESL losses may be (partially) recovered (up to half) using a post-detection (incoherent) integration process [5]. Once the effect of spreading is resolvable by the signal resolution, losses will occur, and as a result, further increases in time or bandwidth will not deliver the predicted gains. Previous work has shown that the background suppression follows theoretical predictions [2]. Here, we focus on the environmental effects on signal losses.

The wideband ambiguity function (AF) is given [6] as

$$\chi(\tau, \beta) = \sqrt{\beta} \cdot e^{j\omega_0\beta\tau} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u(t) u^*[\beta(t + \tau)] e^{j\phi t} dt, \quad (5)$$

where τ is the propagation delay, u is the signal's complex envelope, ω_0 is the center frequency, and β is the time-scale stretch factor given by

$$\beta = \frac{1-v/c}{1+v/c}, \quad (6)$$

where c is the speed of sound in water, v is the radial velocity, and ϕ is the Doppler shift, given by

$$\phi = (1 - \beta)\omega_0. \quad (7)$$

Displaying time and Doppler slices across the 3-d AF we can gain insight into some of the effects of changing signal bandwidth and duration. Figs. 3-6 show theoretical slices of the AF peak for the transmitted LCAS'15 signals to be analyzed later. Note that increasing bandwidth while holding the duration constant produces finer resolution in time (Fig. 3), no change in resolution in Doppler (Fig. 4), and no signal losses. Conversely, increasing time duration while holding the bandwidth constant produces finer resolution in Doppler (Fig. 5), no change in time resolution (Fig. 6), and no signal losses. With this theoretical background, we now explore the effects of an actual acoustic environment on the AF peak levels and widths, to assess when the channel coherence is lost.

Many propagation channels, and acoustic channels in particular, are subject to extreme time spreading and frequency spreading which destroy temporal and spectral coherence of signal propagation. A channel which is spread in either time or frequency, but not the other is known as a "singly spread" channel; a channel which is spread in both time and frequency is known as a "doubly spread" channel. Processing larger time/frequency bands beyond the limits for which the channel is

coherent will not provide the expected theoretical increase in gain, though they may still provide partial gains. We assert that underwater acoustic channels are doubly spread, and we endeavor to understand the amount of spreading in each dimension in order to understand the coherence limits of the channel and to enable the system designer to make suitable choices for HDC signal design and subsequent processing.

Fig. 3. Theoretical effects on AF time resolution of increasing bandwidth while keeping signal duration constant. Quadrupling of bandwidth results in quartering the peak width, without signal losses.

Fig. 4. Theoretical effects on AF Doppler resolution of increasing bandwidth while keeping signal duration constant. Quadrupling of bandwidth results no changes to peak width and no losses.

Fig. 5. Theoretical effects on AF Doppler resolution of increasing time duration while keeping signal bandwidth constant. Quadrupling of duration results in quartering the peak widths, without signal losses.

Fig. 6. Theoretical effects on AF Doppler resolution of increasing time duration while keeping signal bandwidth constant. Quadrupling of duration results no change in peak width and no losses.

III. THE LCAS'15 SEATRIAL DATA

Previous experimentation [2] has shown that one can estimate the coherence limit of the acoustic channel using the CTLFM signal. However, using a single, sub-banded CTLFM waveform, there is no way to determine if the channel's coherence limit is due to time spreading only or due to Doppler spreading only ('singly spread' channel), or spreading in both time and Doppler ('doubly spread' channel). This is because whatever portion of the waveform cycle is processed is scaled equivalently in both time and bandwidth. To separate these two phenomena, a dedicated environmental experiment was conducted to estimate the underwater channel coherence for both time and Doppler as part of the LCAS'15 sea trial. Signals which vary time and bandwidth independently were used. An alternative approach to the one presented here uses a train of short FMs to compute the scattering function for underwater acoustic communication channels [7].

This LCAS'15 sea trial was conducted in September, 2015, in shallow waters off the coast of La Spezia, Italy, in conjunction with an international research project with the Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation (CMRE). Water depths were about 100-200 meters and reverberation-limited conditions were predominant. The CMRE research vessel RV ALLIANCE towed an acoustic source capable of HDC and PAS transmission over the frequency band of 1800-3400Hz. It also towed a monostatic hydrophone receiver array. Various HDC and PAS runs were conducted with the RV LEONARDO ship towing an echo repeater system. In addition, specific runs were executed to investigate the underwater channel coherence.

Fig. 7. shows the geometry for run E12. RV Alliance sailed to the northwest at about 3.5 kts, with the sonar source deployed at 50 meters depth. The E/R track is shown (in red), however for this analysis, we investigate only one-way propagation path from the source to a single hydrophone, suspended in the water column at position BBN2. The ship starts out closing the receive hydrophone, then passes by the closest-point-of-approach (CPA), and then opens away from the receiver.

The following wavetrains of successive LFM's were used: constant time (cT) duration (0.25 sec) with increasing

bandwidth, and constant bandwidth (cB) (6.25 Hz) with increasing time duration, as listed in Tables I and II, respectively. The constant time duration of 0.25s was intended to be short enough that Doppler spreading would not impact the time-spread analysis. Likewise, the constant bandwidth of 6.25 Hz was selected to be small enough that time spreading would not significantly impact the Doppler-spread analysis. As a result, these waveforms are not considered high TB (maximum TB=400) compared to PAS waveforms, which may be an order of magnitude larger. The center frequency for each waveform was 2600 Hz, with bandwidths contained within the range of 1800-3400Hz. It is seen that the changes in time and bandwidth cover a large span, quadrupling from one waveform in the wavetrain to the next. This was done to ensure that we successfully bracketed wherever the point of coherence loss would occur. Using these signals we can compare the channel's effects on received signals with changes in bandwidth or duration without the impact of changes in the other. The waveforms can be considered PAS transmissions in terms of there being a short quiet period between each transmission in order to facilitate clean matched filter correlations without interference of subsequent transmissions in the post analysis. Each of the time-varying waveforms was scaled in amplitude to produce equal energy, so that comparisons between waveforms will capture the relative losses between the signals. In addition, just prior to each waveform, a common reference LFM signal (3500-3600 Hz, 0.5 sec duration) was transmitted to provide a way to estimate transmission loss (TL) for each ping time; any variations in received level of these pings can then be used to compensate (remove the effects) of TL variations due to changes in range or environment over the course of the run in the analysis. Fig. 8 shows the received signals at the hydrophone for the entire run. Each cT wavetrain was cyclically transmitted 8 times over the course of the run, and each cB wavetrain 10 times. It is seen that the received levels peak around mid-run when the source-to-receiver range (and transmission loss) is minimum.

Fig. 7. Fig. 7. LCAS'15 run E12 geometry. Ship trajectory is in black, BBN2 marks the location of the suspended hydrophone used in the analysis; E/R trajectory is in red (not used in this analysis).

Fig. 8. LCAS'15 run E12 transmitted signals received on BBN2 hydrophone.

TABLE I. LCAS'15 WAVEFORMS WITH CONSTANT TIME DURATION

Name	Signal Duration T (sec)	Signal Bandwidth B (Hz)	Time-Bandwidth Product TB
cT1	0.25	6.25	1.56
cT2	0.25	25	6.25
cT3	0.25	100	25
cT4	0.25	400	100
cT5	0.25	1600	400

TABLE II. LCAS'15 WAVEFORMS WITH CONSTANT BANDWIDTH

Name	Signal Duration T (sec)	Signal Bandwidth B (Hz)	Time-Bandwidth Product TB
cB1	0.25	6.25	1.56
cB2	1	6.25	6.25
cB3	4	6.25	25
cB4	16	6.25	100
cB5	64	6.25	400

IV. AMBIGUITY FUNCTION EXAMPLES

Fig. 9. shows examples of received AFs for a set of sequentially transmitted, constant time, variable bandwidth waveforms (cT2, cT3, and cT4). Each AF is constructed by cross-correlating the received one-way signal arrival with a bank of shaded, dopplerized replicas (Doppler resolutions were 0.02, 0.04, and 0.2 Hz for the 25, 100, and 400 Hz sweeps, respectively). The dopplerization is achieved by taking the zero-Doppler replica and applying the appropriate time scaling (contraction or dilation) and frequency shifting. The images are compared to the theoretical AFs, which are obtained by correlating the zero-Doppler replica (transmitted signal) with the Dopplerized replica bank. All images are intensity scaled for comparison. The theoretical AFs show that as bandwidth is increased, the time resolution correspondingly improves (by a factor of 4 with each quadrupling of bandwidth) and the Doppler resolution remains unchanged. Also the time/range bias errors reduce when Doppler is mismatched, as seen by the change in slope of the correlation ridge [8].

Comparing these to the received data AFs it is immediately clear that the acoustic channel induces time multipath or spreading. When bandwidth increases, the time resolution improves, which enables resolution of the various, distinct multipaths. The time spreading effect of the channel effect is more prominently observable with larger bandwidth, and is seen to be over about a 200 ms duration (for one-way propagation). This can be seen in better detail in Fig. 10, which shows a time slice of the ambiguity function (at the peak of the AF surface). None of the multipath spread is observable with the 6.25Hz waveform, but as bandwidth increases the resolution gets finer and the multipath structure is revealed. The peak levels drop, indicative of the energy splitting due to multipath propagation being resolved across multiple processing bins. The impact of these multipaths are also seen in the Doppler dimension. Additionally, the peak widths, as measured at the 10-dB down points (red circles), are observed to get narrower in time as theory would predict, but fail to achieve the factor of four narrowing that would be predicted, due to these multipath losses. Fig. 11. shows that the peak resolutions are all similar but there are multiple copies corresponding to the time multipath mapping into the Doppler dimension as artifacts. This results in an effective widening of the peak widths once the Doppler coherence of the channel cannot support any further signal length. This could be misinterpreted as Doppler spread, when in fact it is caused by time spreading. The AF slices shown here can be compared with theoretical results shown in Figs. 3-4.

Fig. 9. AF examples for constant time duration for theory (left) and data (right); bandwidth is quadrupled from 25 Hz (top) to 100 Hz (middle) to 400Hz (bottom).

Fig. 10. Time slice of the data AF peaks, showing increased time resolution and environmental multipath for constant time duration and quadrupling of bandwidth. The red markers show estimated 10 dB down points.

Fig. 11. Time multipath in Fig. 10, as manifested in the Doppler dimension of the AF.

Fig. 12. shows examples of received AFs for a set of sequentially transmitted, constant bandwidth, variable time waveforms (cB2, cB3, and cB4), compared with those predicted without channel effects. Here, the theoretical AFs show that as time duration is increased, the Doppler resolution correspondingly improves (by a factor of 4 with each quadrupling of time) and the bandwidth resolution remains unchanged. Also the time/range bias errors increase with increasing time duration. The received data AFs show that the acoustic channel induces some Doppler spreading, which is more observable when there is finer Doppler resolution than the width of the environmental Doppler spread. In the Doppler spread case we observe the Doppler spreading is more of a smearing effect than it is a set of discrete arrivals like seen in the time multipath case. There appears to be about 0.5 kts Doppler spread for this example in this environment.

Fig. 13 and 14, show the corresponding Doppler and time slices of the ambiguity function (at the peak of the AF surface), respectively. None of the Doppler spread is observable with the 0.25 sec waveform, but as time increases the resolution gets finer and the Doppler smearing is revealed. We see that above the 4s case, there is Doppler spreading observed which is wider than the signal resolution in this dimension. Although the correlation peaks continue to get narrower with each quadrupling of signal duration, they do not narrow as much as theory (by a factor of

four each time) suggests, due to the spreading losses. We also note the loss in signal level due to energy leakage into surrounding Doppler regions. The impact of this Doppler smearing in the time dimension manifests itself as an artifact that could be confused as time multipath. The AF slices shown here can be compared with theoretical expectations shown in Figs. 5-6.

Fig. 12. AF examples for constant bandwidth for theory (left) and data (right); time duration is quadrupled from 1 s (top) to 4 s (middle) to 16 s (bottom).

Fig. 13. Slice of the data AF peaks, showing increased Doppler resolution and environmental smearing for constant B and quadrupling of time duration.

Fig. 14. Doppler smearing of Fig 13, as manifested in the time delay dimension of the AF.

V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

LCAS'15 run E12 contained 8 transmissions of the cT wavetrains listed in Table I, and 10 transmissions of the cB wavetrains listed in Table II. A statistical analysis was conducted using this data to identify points at which temporal and Doppler coherence are no longer maintained. The following processing and analysis method was used:

- The received signal for each waveform was matched filtered using its corresponding dopplerized replica bank, resulting in the received signal AF. This is also done for the reference waveform.
- The AF maximum is found and its level is recorded.
- Signal receive levels are compensated to remove transmission loss variations: the received level differences of the common reference signal across wavetrains are applied to the received levels of the cB and cT waveforms.
- To aggregate results across the entire period of the run, averages of these relative levels for each waveform are obtained across all transmissions (8 or 10) and differences computed between the average levels of the first waveform in each set/wavetrain with all successive waveform averages.
- The width of the peaks are automatically estimated by finding the -10dB points forward and backward in time (for cT waveforms), and upward and downward in Doppler (for cB waveforms), from the AF peak.

The aggregated results for the 8 cT and 10 cB wavetrain sets are shown in Figs. 15-18 and Tables III and IV, respectively. Fig. 15 shows the peak levels (before TL compensation) for the constant time case, and show the variability amongst each of the waveforms during the run. In general, it is observed that the smaller bandwidth waveforms have the greater receive levels. Fig. 16 shows the estimated peak widths in the time dimension for the constant time case, overlaid with their expected theoretical values. The larger the bandwidth, the larger the deviation from theoretical expectations. The results are summarized in Table III. Without channel losses, the relative receive levels should be the same. Instead, here we see signal losses, a few dB for every quadrupling of bandwidth. The received signal time widths (time extent) are shown as the

average deviation from theory (expressed in both ms and %). We see that as early as 25 Hz (cT2), the channel time spread is causing energy splitting losses and the signal energy is no longer contained within the signal resolution width.

Fig. 17 shows the peak levels (before TL compensation) for the constant bandwidth case. In general, it is observed that the shorter waveforms have the greater receive levels. Fig. 18 shows the estimated peak widths in the Doppler dimension for this case, overlaid with their expected values. The larger the duration, the larger the deviation from theoretical expectations, when viewed as a percentage. The results are summarized in Table IV. The received signal Doppler widths are shown as their average deviation from theory (expressed in both Hz and %). We see signal losses becoming significant between 4 and 16 seconds (cB3 and cB4) in terms of both peak level and width.

Fig. 15. AF peak levels for the cT waveforms.

Fig. 16. Receive signal time extent (width) for the CT waveforms.

Fig. 17. AF peak levels for the cB waveforms for the cB waveforms.

Fig. 18. Receive signal Doppler peak width for the cB waveforms.

TABLE III. SUMMARY OF STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR cT WAVEFORMS.

Name (0.25 s)	B (Hz)	Relative Levels (dB)	Time Extent (ms)	Deviation (%)
cT1	6.25	0	4	2
cT2	25	-2.3	32	31
cT3	100	-4.5	75	301
cT4	400	-5.0	71	1173
cT5	1600	-	-	-

TABLE IV. SUMMARY OF STATISTICAL RESULTS FOR cB WAVEFORMS.

Name (6 Hz)	T (s)	Relative Levels (dB)	Doppler Width (Hz)	Deviation (%)
cB1	0.25	0.00	0.510	9
cB2	1	-0.52	0.310	23
cB3	4	-0.12	0.174	54
cB4	16	-3.09	0.168	210
cB5	64	-5.33	0.096	478

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The LCAS'15 run E12 data examples and statistical analysis has shown the real-world impact of the underwater acoustic environment on the receive signal ambiguity peaks. The peak signal losses in time and Doppler have been shown and quantified. Based on the Tables III and IV, we can estimate that the LCAS'15 acoustic channel supports one-way propagation coherence in Doppler only up to about 25 Hz and in time up to about 4 seconds. For two-way propagation (source to target to receiver) for monostatic or bistatic sonar systems, the spreading effect in time and Doppler is expected to correspondingly increase by about a factor of two. The signal losses (of Tables III and IV) will also be approximately doubled for such sonar configurations. Processing waveforms with greater bandwidth or time than these limits for this environment, will produce signal losses, resulting in SNR gains that are less than expected. In addition, by choosing smaller TB signals to process, Doppler-matched processing will not be required, and many more detection opportunities will be available to more quickly detect and better track a target. Table V presents a summary of the theoretical and practical effects of increases in signal time duration and bandwidth. If future experiments were to be conducted in this environment, the experiment method could be repeated, but with a set of signals more closely bracketing the expected coherence limits of the channel, which would enable a more precise determination of the points at which channel coherence is lost.

TABLE V. SUMMARY OF TIME AND BANDWIDTH EFFECTS

		Increase B (constant T)	Increase T (constant B)
Theoretical Channel	Time Resolution	Better (finer)	No Change
	Doppler Resolution	No Change	Better (finer)
	Time Bias Error	Lower	Higher
Real Underwater Channel	Processing Gain limited by:	Time Spreading	Doppler Spreading
	Spreading Observed in:	Time (due to channel)	Doppler (due to channel)
		Doppler (artifact)	Time (artifact)

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